

THE IMPORTANCE OF NEOLOGISMS IN ENGLISH

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TerDPI katta o'qituvchisi

ANNOTATSIYA:

Ushbu maqolada neologizmlarning paydo bo'lishi, neologizmlarning nutqda qo'llanilishi, ularning tildagi ahamiyati kabilar yoritib berilgan. Undan tashqari neologizmlarning hozirgi kunda keng qo'llanilishi haqida ham aytib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Neologizm, arxaiklar, til evolyutsiyasi, ingliz tili morfologiyasi, so'z yasalishi, yangi so'zlar, oqitish, ta'lim, texnologiya, internet.

ANNOTATION:

This article discusses the emergence of neologisms, their use in speech, their importance in the language, etc. It also discusses the widespread use of neologisms in the English language.

Keywords: Neologisms, archaics, language evolution, English morphology, word formation, new words, teaching, education, technology, internet.

The study on neologisms or the new words created in a language has been gaining strength lately and has been getting the attention of linguists. It is obvious that neologisms produce a feeling of curiosity since they frequently appear in the vocabulary of speakers quite suddenly. For this reason, researchers have tried to explain how they are created and have also tried to classify them into different categories, even though they do not always coincide in their approach. While there is a general awareness of the meaning of neologisms that we use daily, researchers have investigated the reasons for their emergence, the preference that speakers show among competing forms of these new words and how they develop. The main aim of this paper is to understand neologisms in English and in the second place to discuss their role in the classroom of English as a foreign language briefly. In order to do so, based on previous research on the topic, I have classified neologisms into four main categories of neologisms: those that are newly coined terms, when the new word is a word that already exists in the language but with some changes in its form, when the new word has the same form but has undergone some non-formal changes, such as a change in its meaning or grammatical category, and finally when the new word has a foreign source (i.e. has been adopted from another language).

Languages are living entities which evolve over time and the lexicon plays a relevant role in this change because while words cease to be used other new words emerge. Neologisms are the new words that speakers create in a language. They serve to keep the language up-to-date since they generally emerge because of the new situations that need to be referred to, such as new technologies, new situations in politics and new developments. Speakers create and are exposed to neologisms everywhere, for instance, in the news, social media and advertising. Thus, the study of neologisms is of particular interest because they reflect the language that speakers use to talk about new realities and situations. It could be stated that almost all the words in a language were at some point a neologism. This article aims to discuss and analyse the presence of current neologisms in many scenarios of our daily life, with specific reference to English. In order to do so, the structure of the paper will be as follows. In section 2, I will first define the concept of neologism, then in section 3, I will explain how English neologisms are created. In section 4, I will discuss the main areas in which neologisms may be found currently, namely, the fields of technology, science, politics, COVID-19, advertising and the news. Finally, in section 5 I will discuss neologisms from the EFL perspective and I will address the issue of whether teaching neologisms is necessary for EFL students. Some guidelines to teach neologisms in the EFL will be provided.

The word neologism comes from Greek “neo” (new) and “logos” (word). Hence, as its root suggests, a neologism is a new word that has recently been included in the vocabulary of a language. Furthermore, it can also refer to an idiom and an expression that has been incorporated in the speakers’ everyday use of a language. Neologisms are new words, word-combinations or fixed phrases that appear in the language due to the development of social life, culture, science and engineering. Neologisms are also defined “as newly coined lexical units or existing lexical units that acquire a new sense. It is estimated that languages gain 3,000 new words per year, although they are difficult to quantify exactly because some of them tend to arise and vanish rapidly. Generally speaking, when dictionary writers include new words in a dictionary they provide the date in which the neologism was first produced and an explanation about how it was created. When considering whether to include a new word or not, dictionary writers need to take into account the frequency of the neologism in a concrete period of time. The inclusion of neologisms in dictionaries allows speakers to be aware of the existence of these new words, after all, neologisms are part of many speakers’ everyday lexicon and their use is increasingly higher nowadays thanks to the media, language contact, the Internet and globalisation.

The creation of English neologisms reflects English morphology and English morphological processes to a great extent (Behera & Mishra, 2013). In this section, I will discuss the processes which result in the creation of a neologism in English. Drawing from the classification by Behera and Mishra (2013), I have organised them into four main categories. The creation of the new word from scratch, that is to say when a new form with a new meaning is created, when the new word results from making some formal changes to a word that already exists in the language or is built from parts of it (section 3.2.), when the new word takes the same form as the original but has undergone changes to its meaning or grammatical category (section 3.3.), and finally when the new word has a foreign source. Neologisms can also be created by changing the form of an already existing word, and this is the case of the five categories that I will discuss in this section: shortening, compounding, affixation/derivation, and reduplication.

Some neologisms are existing lexical words which have undergone a change which does not affect the form of the original word as it is the case of the categories that I will explain next. First, I will discuss neologisms that have maintained the form of the existing word but have acquired a different meaning, then I will present eponyms, followed by the process of conversion and finally I will explain collocations namely the new combination of words. All languages change over time and the reasons why neologisms arise are diverse. However, the new developments in technology, economy, politics and other new social contexts that have taken place in the 1990s have had a very important impact on the creation of neologisms in English and in languages across the world. The new words that have been created are spread more quickly than ever before (Abbas, 2009) through the Internet in a globalised world and, knowledge, entertainment and culture are also easily transmitted. In this section, I will consider five areas in which many neologisms can be found nowadays: technology/science, political developments, the COVID-19 pandemic, advertising and the news, and we will see some of the processes that were discussed in the previous section at work.

References

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